

8T – Manifolds Heredity

O Manor

September 21, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the 8T which allowed deriving the primordial, the author builds the idea of manifold heredity. That is a new manifold invoked stationary, which departed from the original manifold, must be of the same kind in terms of the number of dimensions it has and its feature. It has to be complete and simply connected.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2A) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

So now instead of the classification of spin we can represent each coupling term to be a mixture of spins of distinct kind. Define spin operator:

$$\mathcal{b}: [\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{Q}] \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_{[\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{Q}]} \quad (1.64)$$

That is a mapping between the integers and non-integer fields onto a spin operator in such way that the spin is matching the subscript:

$$\mathcal{b}: 0 \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_0$$

$$\mathcal{b}: \frac{1}{2} \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_{1/2}$$

$$\mathcal{b}: 1 \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_1$$

Now each coupling term can be represented in a way that reflect the idea of interacting fields, which are represented by spin operators.

$$[(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_0 + \mathcal{S}_{1/2} + \mathcal{S}_1 \quad (1.44.A)$$

Let us analyze the idea of heredity. We have presented a manifold creation as a curvature spike departing from the original manifold, the curvature spike immediately gets flatten by equation (1.2A) as it is part of the packet. The process of flattening due to the packet is the reason for the acceleration at all stages. We have presented the variation of the Dirac Delta. So the Dirac delta in 8T describe the process in which arbitrary amount of curvature appear, and vanish into matter. However, there is no restriction with regard to Time. Arbitrary amount of curvature can appear at any time, so we must modify the idea of the Dirac in our framework.

$$\begin{aligned} \delta g \neq 0 & \quad at \quad t = Q(t) \\ \delta g = 0 & \quad at \quad t_1 = Q(t + \Delta t) \end{aligned}$$

At later continuation of time:

$$t_2 > t_1$$

This condition is satisfied:

$$\delta g \neq 0 \quad at \quad t_2 = Q(t + \Delta t + \Delta t)$$

Moreover, the amount of variations is either prime or one:

$$\delta g = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0$$

The process of manifold creation can be put as means of an arrow:

$$\zeta: \mathcal{S}_n \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_{n+1}$$

The process of birth has an heredity condition, the new manifold must have the same number of dimensions as the original manifold and must possess the same traits, i.e. be a simply connected manifold and a complete manifold. In other words, we can add an additional superscript with the (3,1) signature to the newborn manifold, to ensure the heredity condition.

$$\zeta: \mathcal{S}_n^{(3,1)} \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_{n+1}^{(3,1)}$$

So that is in agreement with the idea of the multiverse as presented in the 8T thesis, i.e. infinite set of surfaces, each with a finite dimensions of it's own. The heredity condition prevents the theoretical scenario in which the newborn manifold will possess a higher number of dimensions or alternatively that the new manifold will not be complete or simply connected. Such is needed as for simplicity sake, if each newborn manifold is of a different class than the packet process of flattening could result in complications. Nature is satisfied with simplicity as the primorial is indicating. What is simpler than generating only one class of manifolds? it is reasonable argument to claim that nature is Lagrangian oriented in the number of manifold classes it generates.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

Manor Ohad